

Pword-report

Language name: **Kharia** [k^hɛ/əɾija] (LID 1750)
Name: Thomas Goldammer
Sources: J. Peterson (p.c.), University of Osnabrück.
K. Rehberg (2003) *Phonologie des Kharia - Prosodische Strukturen und segmentales Inventar*.
University of Osnabrück.
H. S. Biligiri (1965) *Kharia. Phonology, Grammar and Vocabulary*. Puna: Deccan College.
Internet version of The Ethnologue, Vol. 15 (2005). www.ethnologue.com.
Date completed: 13.04.2006

I Language profile

of spks: 293,575
Place: primarily Jharkhand, but also Chhattisgarh, Orissa, Tripura, Assam, West Bengal, Andaman and Nicobar Islands/all India, also some in Nepal
Contact lgs.: Sadani, Oriya (both are *linguae francae* in the Kharia area), Hindi, English (modern superstrates) (all Indo-European), Mundari (related to Kharia), Kurux (Dravidian) (both neighboring lgs.)
Status: not an official language
Prospects: most people are bilingual in Kharia/Sadani or Hindi; starting shift to Sadani or Hindi, maybe endangered
Struct. results: many lexical borrowings, most often the native phonology does not apply to the recent loans

II Morpheme types

1. _____ Stem

2. _____ Semi-restricted post-posed formative

-*ɲ* ~ sometimes -*naɲ* / C_____ ~ -*ɲ* / V_[+back]_____ '1s'

(used as possessive suffix with some N and as A/S agreement marker with V)

- | | | | | | |
|-----|--|-----|--|-----|---|
| (1) | <i>aba=ɲ</i>
father=1s
'my father' | (2) | <i>orej=naɲ</i>
ox=1s
'my ox' | (3) | <i>kayom=ta=ɲ</i>
speak=M.PRS=1s
'I speak.' |
| (4) | <i>um=ɲ</i> <i>kayom=ta</i>
NEG=1s speak=M.PRS
'I do not speak.' | (5) | <i>ho</i> <i>rocho[?]b=k=ɲ</i>
DEM side=M.PT=1s
'I moved to that side.' | | |

3. _____ Unrestricted post-posed formative

=*ga* 'FOC' (attached to whatever is focussed and a phonological word)

- | | | | |
|------|--|------|--|
| (6) | <i>ho</i> <i>rusuɲ</i> <i>oʔ=te=ga</i>
DEM red house=OBL=FOC
'in that red house/that red house _{OBJECT} ' | (7) | <i>ho</i> <i>rusuɲ=ga</i> <i>oʔ=te</i>
DEM red=FOC house=OBL
'in that RED house/that RED house _{OBJECT} ' |
| (8) | <i>karay</i> <i>go[?]d_ɔ=te=ga</i>
do C:TEL=ACTIVE.PRS=FOC
's/he does the job' | (9) | <i>karay=ga</i> <i>go[?]d_ɔ=te</i>
do=FOC C:TEL=ACTIVE.PRS
's/he does the job' |
| (10) | <i>ek</i> <i>tʃho=ga</i>
one CLF=FOC
'one X' | (11) | <i>ek=ga</i> <i>tʃho(=ga)</i>
one=FOC CLF(=FOC)
'ONE X' |

4. _____ Restricted pre-posed formative

kol 'RECP' (only with V) (is called a particle, but always precedes the V immediately, but note that there is some (lexicalized) incorporation of direct objects between *kol* and V stem) (**Note that *kol* is a free prosodic word (cf. Section XI below)!**)

- (12) *kol gil=na*
RECP beat=INF
'to beat each other'
- (13) *kol bheʔto=na=bar*
RECP meet=FUT=2d
'meet each other!, you both will meet each other'

Incorporated nouns can stand between *kol* and the verb stem:

- (14) *kol ulaʔ likha=ki=kiyar*
RECP letter write=MED.PST=d
'they wrote each other letters'
(but: strongly preferred is *ulaʔ kol likha=ki=kiyar*)
- but: (15) **kol tomlij uq=ki=kiyar*
RECP milk drink=MED.PST=d
'they gave each other milk to drink'

5. _____ Restricted pre-/infix

-(o)ʔb- ~ -(o)ʔ- / ___LAB 'CAUS' (one allomorph) (only with V)

With monosyllabic roots it becomes a prefix-like formative and then it gets the *o-* extension.

But the prefix form becomes more and more productive also with polysyllabic bases and is sometimes used additionally to the infix (cf. (22))!

- (16) *oʔb-ʔoʔ*
CAUS-eat
'feed'
- (17) *oʔb-yo*
CAUS-see
'show'
- (18) *oʔ-piʔj*
CAUS-break
'break(tr.)'
- (19) *qo-ʔb-ko*
<CAUS>sit
'cause to sit'
- (20) *re-ʔ-maʔ*
<CAUS>call
'cause to call'
- (21) *se-ʔb-(ʔ)ghor*
<CAUS>be.straight
'straighten'
- (22) possible CAUS forms of *katiʔb* 'gather':
ka-ʔb-tiʔb gather-CAUS-Σ 'cause to gather'
oʔb-katiʔb CAUS-gather 'cause to gather'
oʔb-ka-ʔb-tiʔb CAUS-gather-CAUS-Σ 'cause to gather' (no double CAUS meaning with this verb! (only 3 verbs of this kind))
- (23) *ob-a-ʔb-loʔj*
CAUS-sing-CAUS-Σ
'have s.o. make s.o. sing' (double CAUS meaning with this verb)

6. _____ Restricted infix

-nV- 'ABSTR.NMLZ' (V = root vowel) (only with monosyllabic V)

- (24) *raʔb* 'bury' → *ranaʔb* 'burial ground'
goʔj 'die' → *gonoʔj* 'death'

→ 6 morpheme types

III Syllable

Syllable structure

- In native words, neither a complex onset nor a complex coda is allowed. Thus (C)V/N(C) is the maximum syllable shape. V/N means that a nucleus can either be a vowel (vowel length is not phonemic, but there are diphthongs (cf. (25))) or a syllabic nasal (mostly /ŋ/ (cf. (26a)), rarely /ŋ/ (cf. (26b)), no example for /ɲ/ and /m/.

- (25) *laiʔj* /lāɛj/ → [lāɛʔjⁿ] 'make pregnant'

- (26a) *laphŋga* /lafŋga/ → [lə.pfŋ.ga] 'cave'

- (26b) *phophnda* /fofnda/ → [fo.fŋ.da] 'fungus'

- Onsetless syllables occur only word-initially. Within words, a glide /j/ is inserted (cf. rule 4 below).
- Complex onsets or codas only occur in loans:

- (27) *andhra* /andʰra/ → [an.dʰra] 'make blind' (cf. Sadani *andhr*)
aŋk /aŋk/ → [aŋk] 'act (of a play)' (cf. Hindi *āk*)

Monomoraic words

- Underlyingly monomoraic words surface as bimoraic, due to the word-final lengthening rule affecting vowels and some consonants (cf. rule 10 below).

- (28) *si* /si/ → [si:] 'plow (v)'

- Proto-Munda is said to have had a bimoraic word requirement, which is preserved in Kharia. Monosyllabic(!) verb roots undergo reduplication in subordination whereas polysyllabic roots remain unchanged.

Vowel-initial words

- (29) *oreʔ* [ɔreʔʲ] 'ox' (but note rule 9 below!)

Polysyllabic morphemes

- (30) *laphŋga* 'cave'
 (31) *=kiyar* 'DU'

Phonotactics

- Word-initially, /r ʈ ŋ/ are said to be not allowed (cf. *Aroma* 'city of Rome'), /w/ occurs word-initially, but only in loans. But in the dictionary there are lots of words with initial [r] *raʔb* 'bury' (native!). Rehberg (2003:15) also states that /r/ is not allowed in onset position generally.
- /s h/ do not occur in coda position in native words, but there are some loans: *bes* 'good', *sandeh* 'doubt'

Superheavy syllables

Only word-finally in loans:

- (32) *jhāūt* 'animal'
 (33) *aŋk* 'act (of a play)'

IV Tone & Stress

Tone

There is no evidence for distinctive tone in Kharia.

Stress

Kharia has no expiratory accent and also within the prosodic foot, any syllable may be more "prominent" in its intensity. (Peterson p.c.)

Rehberg (2003), however, states that stress is always on the first syllable of a word and is a lower pitch, whereas unstressed syllables have higher pitch.

The foot structure is described in Section XI below.

V Other Non-concatenative Processes

Ablaut: Some verbs form their middle voice stem by ablaut:

- (34) *laʔdha* 'load onto sth.'
laʔdhe 'be loaded onto sth.'

List of phonological processes

1. _____ Intervocalic flapping

/d^(h)/ → [ɾ^(h)] / V__V (described this way by Peterson (p.c.))

(but minimal pair *oʔoʔ* 'more', *oʔoʔ* 'get stuck', thus, the process remains unclear)

Domain: stem+enclitic, no examples for stem+stem, no transcription available for prefix+stem examples

(35) $d\text{or}=e$ take=ACTIVE.IRR 'take!' but: (36) $d\text{o}^?d=na$ take=INF 'to take'

(37) $o\text{-}d\text{am}$ CAUS-arrive 'bring'

((37) would be an example for prefix+stem. So probably the flapping rule does not apply with prefix+stem.)

2. Coda neutralization

Peterson (p.c.) states that [voiced], [aspirated], [anterior] and [alglottal] are neutralized in coda position (to +vcd, -asp, -ant, +glott), but on the other hand he provided words like *algaṭ* 'clearly', *buidh* 'intelligence, idea' (which strangely comes from Sadani *budhi*), *kitab* 'book'. However, (nearly?) all of the counterexamples are loans. Rehberg (2003), however, writes that only plain voiced stops are preglottalized in coda position. But she also remarks that the preglottalization in coda position often not applies in fast speech.

2a. /b/ → [ʔb^m] / _____o (possibly not in recent loans?)

(38) *kati^b* /kaṭib/ → [kaṭiʔb^m] 'gather'

2b. /d d/ → [ʔd^h] / _____o (possibly not in recent loans?)

(39) *la^d* /lad/ → [laʔd^h] 'bake'

2c. /j/ → [ʔjⁿ] / _____o (possibly not in recent loans?)

(40) *tij* /tiḡ/ → [tiʔjⁿ] 'side'

2d. /g/ → [ʔ] / _____o (possibly not in recent loans?)

(41) *la[?]* /lag/ → [laʔ^a] 'cut (plants, wood)' (cf. Hindi *lag*)

but: *lakh=ol* /lag+og/ → [lək^hʔ^o] 'cut_{PAST}'
(N.B. the PST suffix =ol causes devoicing+aspirating of preceding voiced(!) stops.)

(42) *ol* /og/ → [ɔ:ʔ^o] 'house'

but: *og=al* /og=ag/ → [ɔgʔ^a] 'house+GEN'

3. Cluster simplification

$C \rightarrow \emptyset / C_C, C_C$ _o

In native words, complex codas and onsets are not allowed. Some morphemes have underlying consonant clusters and are simplified in those contexts where a complex onset or coda would occur:

(43) *likha=te[?]d=ijn* write=PROG.ACTIVE=1s 'I am writing' but: (44) *likha=te[?]j=ki* write=PROG.ACTIVE=3p 'they are writing'

(45) *col=si[?]d=ijn* go=PERF=1s 'I have gone' but: (46) *col=si[?]* go=PERF[3s] 's/he has gone'

4. Glide insertion

$\emptyset \rightarrow [j w] / (w)(X)V_V(X)$ ([w] is inserted, if both vowels are back (/a o u/), otherwise [j] is inserted)
(with the PST =ol always [j] is inserted, also after back vowels)

(47) *u* 'DEM' + =a[?] 'GEN' → *uwa[?]* 'of this'

(48) *yo* 'see' + =e 'ACTIVE.IRR' → *yoye* 's/he will see'

(49) *o-* 'CAUS' + eḡ 'return (itr.)' → *oyeḡ* 'bring back'

(50) *yo* 'see' + =ol 'PST' → *yoyo[?]* 's/he saw'

5. Front vowel deletion

/i e/ → Ø / ___=V, V=___ (i and e of clitics are deleted adjacent to other vowels)

- (51) *koŋ=te=jar* vs. (52) *koŋ=t=ijn*
 know=ACTIVE.PRS=1de know=ACTIVE.PRS=1s
 'we_{excl.} both know' 'I know'

But: =e after V undergoes glide insertion instead:

- (53) *i=ye=niŋ*
 what=ACTIVE.IRR=1pi
 'what shall we_{incl.} do?'

6. Resyllabification

...C+V... → ...(_oCV...

- (54) The CAUS prefix *oʔb-* seems to be realized as *ob-* [ɔb] before vowels. (Peterson p.c.)
 Would /b/ stay in coda position, it would be realized as [ʔb^m], cf. rule 2 above.

- (55) *likha=teʔd=ijn* but: (56) *likha=teʔj(*d)=ki*
 write=PROG.ACTIVE=1s write=PROG.ACTIVE=3p
 'I am writing' 'they are writing'

(Onset or coda clusters are not allowed. Thus in (55) must have applied a resyllabification.)

- (57) *og=aʔ* /og=ag/ → [ɔ.gɑʔ^a] 'house+GEN'

7. Word-final vowel insertion

Ø → [ə] / C___# (specific to speaker, can also apply in fast speech)

- (58) /moŋ/ → [mɔŋ(ə)] 'one'
 /ikud/ → [ikud(ə)] 'very' (no preglottalization(!))

8. Word-initial prenasalization

/b d d_ɹ g/ → [ʰb ʰd ʰd_ɹ ʰg] / #___ (specific to speaker)

- (59) /batae-na/ → [(ʰ)bataɛnɑ] 'to tell'

9. Word-initial glottal stop insertion

Ø → [ʔ] / #___V (specific to speaker)

- (60) /ijn/ → [(ʔ)ijŋ] 'I'

10. Word-final lengthening

V → V: / ___#

- (61) *si* /si/ → [si:] 'plow (v)'

VI "Free" Grammatical Morphemes

A *Prefix+Stem*

Rule 1: unclear, probably no application

Rule 2: applies (with C-initial stems, otherwise rule 4 or 6 applies)

Rule 3: no example because no prefix ends in CC

Rule 4: applies

Rule 5: no example because no prefix ends in a front vowel

Rule 6: applies

Rules 7-10: no data

Foot assignment: prefixes are part of the stem-pword (Peterson p.c.)

B Stem+Clitic

Rule 1: applies

Rule 2: applies (with C-initial clitics, otherwise rule 4 or 6 applies)

Rule 3: applies (but not with =oʔ 'ACTIVE.PST')

Rule 4: applies

Rule 5: applies

Rule 6: applies

Rules 7-10: no data

Foot assignment: Monosyllabic clitics form a foot together with monosyllabic bases. Two or more clitics together form a foot, but not with the stem.

VII Polymorphemic Stem forms

The PST suffix -oʔ ~ -yoʔ / V___ causes devoicing+aspirating of preceding voiced(!) stops, even if another consonant intervenes underlyingly, as in /=sigd/ 'PERF' (thus rule 3 applies first):

(62) *qam* *qel=sikh=oʔ*
arrive come=PERF=ACTIVE.PST
'It (the day) had arrived.'

(63) *col=sitq=ijn*
go=PERF=1s
'I have gone'

For rule 3, this suffix -(y)oʔ is treated as having an onset consonant (which, however, does not surface). Thus, the cluster simplification applies (as (62) shows).

VIII Compounds, Concatenations, Juxtapositions

Compounding:

(64) *paisa-qhebuwa*
money-money
'wealth'

(65) *goyŋij-oʔ*
cook-house
'kitchen'

No information, whether or not resyllabification (and, to that effect, the other rules) applies (e.g. in (65)). Every part retains its prosodic structure.

Incorporation:

(66) *kol* *ulaʔ-likha=ki=kiyar*
RECP letter-write=MED.PST=d
'they wrote each other letters'
(but: strongly preferred is *ulaʔ kol likha=ki=kiyar*)

but: (67) **kol* *tomlij* *uq=ki=kiyar*
RECP milk drink=MED.PST=d
'they gave each other milk to drink'

No information, which rules apply.

IX Reduplication

In subordination or as lexical head of a complement, stems undergo full reduplication if they are monosyllabic:

(68) *ijn=aʔ* *yo-yo* *lebu*
1s=GEN see~SUBORD person
'the person I saw/see/will see/should see...'

(69) *oʔ=yaʔ* *bay~bay* *um=ijn* *baʔj=ta*
house=GEN build~CPLMT NEG=1s like=MED.PRS
'I don't like house building.'

If the stems are disyllabic, they remain unchanged. This is due to the already mentioned Proto-Munda minimal word requirement (2 morae).

Another type of reduplication can be used for intensifying. A stem with a suffix can be fully reduplicated:

- (70) *badke-ga~badke-ga*
[badkegabadkega]
hurry-FOC~INTENS
'hurry tremendously'

Every reduplication part retains its own prosodic structure, but the first reduplicant is on a slightly higher pitch than the second one.

X Phrase/Sentence-level phenomena

"Pitch level gradually decreases throughout the entire utterance." (p. 33) At the end of the utterance, this decrease overlays the rising pitch of the last feet. In questions, the foot LH pitch is pronounced clearly through the whole utterance, i.e. there is no decrease.

XI Other Special things

Geminates:

- Geminates are only possible with an intervening morpheme boundary. But then, there are minimal pairs, such as *u=na?* [ʊnaʔ^a] 'this=GEN' vs. *un=na=?* [ʊn:ɑʔ^a] 'place=INF=GEN'
- /s h/ cannot be geminated.

Foot:

- Feet are mostly bisyllabic, but also mono- and trisyllabic feet can occur (*o?* 'house', *khariya* 'Kharia')
- Feet are marked by a LH contour with a falling pitch at the very end. Clitics are outside the foot structure (except sometimes when the host is monosyllabic). If two clitics are attached to a host, they can form a foot together (but this needs further research).
- The preposed particle *kol* 'RECP' forms an own foot.
- All lexical morphemes including the postpositions form a single foot (maybe together with affixes but excluding clitics), may it be mono-, bi- or trisyllabic.